

EVALUATION OF LIPID PROFILE AS PREDICTOR BIOMARKER FOR CARDIOVASCULAR DISORDER IN DIABETIC MELLITUS TYPE-II PATIENT

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18081519>

Keywords

Diabetic Mellitus Type II, cardiovascular disorder, Lipid Profile

Article History

Received: 01 November 2025

Accepted: 15 December 2025

Published: 29 December 2025

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Abstract

Background: Diabetic Mellitus Type-II is multi metabolic disorder. Hyperglycemia condition slowly damage Cardiovascular disease (CVD) system. Research has proved that through biomarkers CVD disorder could be diagnosed at early stage of complications. The aims of this study was to determine the frequency of cardiovascular disorders in Diabetic Mellitus Type-II patients and to find out the abnormalities in cardiac biomarkers and lipid profile parameters and also evaluate the role of cardiac markers for the assessment of pre cardiovascular complication in Diabetic Mellitus Type-II patients.

Material & Methods: This research was carried out at Institute of Biochemistry University of Sindh Jamshoro. Total 200 cases were selected, 100 Diabetic subjects and 100 non diabetic healthy controls including (males and females) age between 30 to 60 years were selected in the study. All samples were collected from OPD clinics of Liaquat University of Medical Health Sciences (LUMHS) Hyderabad/Jamshoro and ISRA University Hospital Hyderabad. All biochemical parameters of Diabetic subjects and controls were analyzed on C311, Hitachi 902 Roche company automatic analyzer by spectrophotometer method.

Results: Total 200 subjects were selected in the study, 100 Diabetes Mellitus Type II patients and 100 non diabetic healthy controls were selected. Male were found 63% and female were found 37%, while in non diabetic healthy controls group males were found 66% and females were found 34%. The Mean±SD age of diabetic patients was 47.2±7.3years and control group Mean±SD of age 42.3±8.3 years. Mean±SD was calculated for Age, BMI, BP, all biochemical markers and analyzed respectively.

Conclusion: All Diabetic subjects were divided into three groups. Present study showed that, the level of HbA1c, BMI, BP, Cholesterol, Triglyceride and LDL have been observed higher in 2nd Group, and HDL found lower.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes Mellitus Type-II is the condition of hyperglycemia due to the insulin resistance and impaired secretion of insulin hormone. Chronic condition of hyperglycemia or diabetes cause the dysfunctioning of vital organ such as kidneys, eyes, heart etc etc (Joseph et al; 2023). Several pathogenic processes are involved in the

development of diabetes, these ranges from autoimmune destruction of the β -cells of the pancreas with consequent insulin deficiency that results in resistance to insulin action (Cade, 2008). Insulin resistance leads to various metabolic conditions like increase cholesterol level, dyslipidemia decrease different hormones

etc (Cochran et al; 2021).The prevalence of Diabetes Mellitus is rising all over the world due to the population growth, life style, aging, urbanization and obesity. Diabetes Mellitus is a major source of morbidity and mortality it increases the risk of development of acute and chronic metabolic complication such as diabetic ketoacidosis, hypoglycemia, coronary heart disease, retinopathy, nephropathy, foot ulceration and cardiovascular disease (Chaitet al., 2024). Cardiovascular disease is more prevalent in Diabetes Mellitus Type-II patients. Diabetes with dyslipidemia will be strong risk factor of cardiovascular diseases (Jaiswal et al., 2014). Atherosclerosis is the main cause of death in the world among the all types of cardiovascular diseases. Atherosclerotic vascular disease is the thickness of cardiovascular arteries, which may become more complicated due to of diabetes (Rye, 2014). Patients with Diabetes Mellitus Type-II (DMTII) frequently exhibit macro vascular hurdle for atherosclerotic cardiovascular (CV) disease (Kostapanos and Elisaf, 2014). Low levels of HDL cholesterol (HDL-C) independently risk factor of cardiovascular (CV) disease and coronary heart disease but high levels of high-density lipoproteins (HDL) are found protective against atherosclerosis (Niroumand et al., 2016). Alteration in lipid profile is common in Diabetes Mellitus type-II patients, this condition cause atherosclerosis in patients (von Eckardstein et al; 2023). Patients with diabetes have two to four fold higher cardiovascular risk as compare to non diabetes (Hoang et al; 2022). Due to higher risk of Diabetes Mellitus to cardiovascular disease, the measurement of triglyceride (TG), high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDLc), total cholesterol (TC), low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDLc) are important biomarkers which predict CVDs (Zhan et al., 2014). Triglyceride (TG) levels can be used as predictor for cardiovascular diseases (Zhan et al.,2014). Patients with higher level triglycerides and total cholesterol in Diabetes Mellitus Type-II (DMT-II) patients will be high risk factor for cardiovascular disorders (Shah and Arneja, 2013). Merino et al., 2014, Hirayama and Miida, 2012 also reported that high level of low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDLc) is a major risk factor for atherosclerotic

cardiovascular disease, other risk factors, including family history, smoking, obesity, lack of exercise and high level of blood pressure with Diabetes Mellitus cause cardiovascular disorders (Brown and Doris, 2016). The aims of this study to determine the frequency of cardiovascular disorders in Diabetic Mellitus Type-II patients and to find out the abnormalities in cardiac biomarkers and lipid profile parameters and explore the role of cardiac markers for the assessment of pre cardiovascular complication in Diabetic Mellitus Type-II patients.

Material and Method.

This research was conducted at the Institute of Biochemistry University of Sindh Jamshoro from January 2023 to June 2025. Institutional ethical committee (vide reference no. IOB/302d/2023 dated 02-01-2023) approved this study. Informed consent was signed by all subjects (control and patients). Diabetes samples were collected from OPD/clinics of Liaquat University Hospital Jamshoro/Hyderabad and ISRA University Hospital Hyderabad. Blood Pressure (Systolic & Diastolic), Body Mass Index (BMI) was calculated by all subjects. All Diabetic subjects were taken detailed clinical history to fill out the questionnaire which consist age, gender, signs and symptom etc. Diabetic patients were age between 30-60 years, having the level of HbA1c was more than 6% were selected for study. Diabetic subjects who were age below 30 years and above 60 years and patients who suffering from malignancy, heart diseases, kidney disease, tuberculosis and Diabetes Mellitus Type-I with ketoacidosis condition were excluded from the study. 3 ml venous blood sample was drawn into the Na-Fluoride tube for quantitative estimation of GluF had 12-14 hours fasting condition and 3 ml blood was drawn in postprandial condition (after 2 hrs breakfast) for estimation of GluR levels. 3 ml blood sample was collected in Ethylene Diamine Tetra Acetic Acid (EDTA) for the assessment of HbA1c, 5 ml venous blood sample was drawn in jell tubes for quantitative determination of Lipid profile and Cardiac Biomarkers, serum was separated and preserved at -20 c. Glucose Fasting (GluF), Glucose Random (GluR), Glycated Haemoglobin level

(HbA1c), and lipid profile (cholesterol, Triglycerides, LDL cholesterol, HDL cholesterol) were measured on automatic analyzer Hitachi 902 with Spectrophotometer method and HbA1c level was measured on Cobas C311 Roche Pakistan Limited automated instrument with Spectrophotometer method.

Result

In this study total 200 cases having 100 Diabetic Mellitus Type 11 patients and 100 controls including (males and females) age between 30 to 60 years were selected in the study. In the Diabetic subjects, males were observed 63 (63%) and female were found 37(37%), in control group male were found 66 (66%) and female were found 34(34%) in the study. The mean standard deviation (Mean±SD) of Diabetic subjects was calculated for Age 47.2±7.3, Blood Pressure (systolic& diastolic) 141.4±8.1 and 84.0±6.3, BMI 25.9±1.5while in control Mean±SD for Age 42.3± 8.3, Blood Pressure (systolic& diastolic) 135.0±8.9and79±5.4, BMI 24.9±0.8were analyzed. Result of diabetic parameters, lipid profile and cardiac cardiac biomarker or cardaic Enzymes of 200 cases (Diabetic subjects &non

diabetic healthy Controls) were determined having result of Mean±SD of GluF 159.7±38.6, Mean±SD of GluR 258.6±57.0, Mean±SD of HbA1c 9.0±1.8, Mean±SD of Chol 188.1±31.4, Mean±SD of Trig 193.6±52.1, Mean±SD of HDL 35.8±6.9, Mean±SD of LDL 112.4±18.1, Mean±SD ofGluF 94.6±9.1, mean±SD of GluR 137.8±8.7, Mean±SD of HbA1c 5.4±0.3, Mean±SD ofChol 179.5±29.6, Mean±SD of Trig172.9±36.2, Mean±SD of HDL40.2±11.7 Mean±SD of LDL 104.1±8.7. In the 1stgroup result was analyzed as Mean±SD ofHbA1c 8.6±1.9, BP (systolic & diastolic) 139.7±8.5 and 81.2±7.6, BMI 25.6±1.7, Chol 186.6±23.8, Trig 187.3±43.0, LDLc 111.2±16.1, HDLc 37.5±7.2.While in the 2nd group result was Mean±SD of HbA1c9.3±1.7, BP (systolic & diastolic)141.8±7.7 and 83.2±6.1, BMI26.0±1.6, Chol 190.5±33.7, Trig 196.5±50.1, LDLc 117.4±17.5, HDLc 35.5±5.6, Whereas in the 3rd group, the result was detected Mean±SD of HbA1c9.0±1.9, BP (systolic & diastolic)140.7±8.3 and 82.4±5.8, BMI25.8±1.4, Chol 183.3±24.9, Trig 184.9±42.7, LDLc 105.3±16.4 and HDLc 36.3±6.4 were analyzed.

Figure 1 Gender wise distribution of Diabetic subjects and control

Table 1: Age and other parameter of Diabetic Mellitus-II subjects and control

Parameters n=200	mean±SD DMT-11 n=100	mean±SD n=100	Control	P value
Age in years	47.2±7.3	42.3± 8.3		0.26
BP (Systolic) mmHg	141.4±8.1	135.0±8.9		0.09
BP (Diastolic) mmHg	84.0±6.3	79±5.4		0.20
BMI kg/m ²	25.9±1.5	24.9±0.8		0.31

Table 2: Result of Diabetic subjects and Control group (n=200)

Parameters n=200	mean±SD DMT-11 n=100	mean±SD n=100	Control	P value
GluF mg/dl	159.7±38.6	94.6±9.1		0.73
GluR mg/dl	258.6±57.0	137.8±8.7		0.69
HbA1c %	9.0±1.8	5.4±0.3		0.03
Cholesterol mg/dl	188.1±31.4	179.5±29.6		0.06
Triglycerides mg/dl	193.6±52.1	172.9±36.2		0.24
HDLc mg/dl	35.8±6.9	40.2±11.7		0.22
LDLc mg/dl	112.4±18.1	104.1±8.7		0.22

Table 3: Age wise distribution of diabetic subjects

Parameters n=100	1 st group n=24	2 nd group n=43	3 rd group n=33
Age in years	30-40 years	41-50 years	51-60 years
HbA1c%	8.6±1.9	9.3±1.7	9.0±1.9
BP (systolic) mmHg	139.7±8.5	141.8±7.7	140.7±8.3
BP (diastolic) mmHg	81.2±7.6	83.2±6.1	82.4±5.8
BMI kg/m ²	25.6±1.7	26.0±1.6	25.8±1.4
Cholesterol mg/dl	186.6±23.8	190.5±33.7	183.3±24.9
Triglycerides mg/dl	187.3±43.0	196.5±50.1	184.9±42.7
HDLc mg/dl	37.5±7.2	35.5±5.6	36.3±6.4
LDLc mg/dl	111.2±16.1	117.4±17.5	105.3±16.4

Figure: correlation HbA1c- HDL $r=0.168$, HbA1c- LDL $r= 0.44$, HbA1c- Trig $r=0.230$, HbA1c-Chol $r=0.197$

Discussions:

The Diabetes Mellitus (DM) increasing day by day worldwide¹. It was also estimated by the international diabetes federation that 592 million (1 in 10 persons) worldwide will have DM by 2035². Diabetes Mellitus type-II increasing with complications³. Diabetes caused macrovascular and microvascular complications such as retinopathy, neuropathy, coronary artery disease, myocardial infarction^{3, 4}. Cardiovascular disorders closely linked with Diabetes which cause mortality and morbidity^{5, 6}. Cardiovascular diseases were found more in male than female⁷. The primary goal of diabetes treatment should be to improve the cardiovascular (CV) risk of diabetic patients. CVD risk factors including obesity, hypertension and dyslipidemia are common in patients with DM. In this study, 100 Diabetic Mellitus Type II patients selected, male were

observed 63% and female were found 37%, while in healthy control group male were found 66 (66%) and female were found 34%, All the data was entered and analyzed on SPSS program version 21.0 the mean standard deviation of Diabetic subjects were calculated (shown in table) for Age 47.2 ± 7.3 years, Blood Pressure (systolic & diastolic) 141.4 ± 8.1 and 84.0 ± 6.3 mmHg, Body Mass Index (BMI) 25.9 ± 1.5 kg/m². Table no. 2 and 3 showed Glucose Fasting (GluF) 159.7 ± 38.6 mg/dl, Glucose Random (GluR) 258.6 ± 57.0 mg/dl, Glycated Hemoglobin A1c (HbA1c) 9.0 ± 1.8 %, Cholesterol (Chol) 188.1 ± 31.4 mg/dl, Triglycerides (Trig) 193.6 ± 52.1 mg/dl, High Density Lipoprotein (HDL) 35.8 ± 6.9 mg/dl, Low Density Lipoprotein (LDL) 112.4 ± 18.1 mg/dl. 68% Diabetic patients were found overweight and Obese. increased BMI was found in good glycemic control as compared to fair and

uncontrolled diabetic patients. Research also revealed that the Blood Pressure (systolic & Diastolic), Body Mass Index (BMI) Lipid Profile (Cholesterol, Triglycerides and Low Density Lipoprotein (LDL) of Diabetic patients were significantly increased as compared to control group while High Density Lipoprotein (HDL) was found significantly decreased as compared to control group. Result of HbA1c, BMI, Blood Pressure (systolic & diastolic) of Diabetic female patients were found higher than Diabetic male patients, while chol, Trig and LDL was found higher in males as compared to females diabetic patients and HDL found lower in male patients. The level of HbA1c, BMI, Blood Pressure (systolic & diastolic), Chol, Trig and LDL have been observed higher in age group 41-50 years than age group of 30-40 and 51-60 years of Diabetic patients while HDL found lower in 2nd group. Present study is similar with the study of Ullasani Kolhar and Priyank and Abdul razaq, et al; 2017. Same results were reported by American Diabetes Association (2023). Ramasamy: et al.; 2024, his research showed that parameters of cardiac biomarker are significantly increased in diabetic patients as compared non diabetic patients. Our study showed positive correlation between diabetic markers with dyslipidaemia. Sushil et al.; 2022) he also find out the positive correlation between glycemic parameters and lipid profile in the study. Correlation showed in figure: 2, 3,4 and 5.

Conclusion:

In this research 63% were males and 37% were females. 68% Diabetic patients were found overweight and Obese. Results showed that the Blood Pressure (systolic & Diastolic), Body Mass Index (BMI) Lipid Profile (Cholesterol, Triglycerides and Low-Density Lipoprotein (LDL) of Diabetic patients were significantly increased as compared to control while High Density Lipoprotein (HDL) was found significantly decreased as compared to control. Result of HbA1c, BMI, Blood Pressure (systolic & diastolic) of Diabetic female patients were found higher than Diabetic male patients, while cholesterol, Triglyceride and LDL was found higher in males as compared to females diabetic patients and HDL found lower in male patients. In the present study, statistically non-

significant positive correlation was found in Diabetic patients of HbA1C, Cholesterol, LDLc and statistically positive correlation with Triglyceride respectively whereas statistically negative correlation was found of HbA1C with HDL respectively.

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